

Development of Mesh Tally Amalgamation Algorithm for Coupled High Fidelity Multiphysics Simulation

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ABSTRACT

For high fidelity multiphysics analysis, Monte Carlo (MC) neutron transport is considered the gold standard in nuclear engineering. However, resolving spatial gradients for any targeted tally from MC often requires significant computing power and a fine mesh, which can lead to higher statistical uncertainty. One way to adjust this cost is to use an optimum mesh which will only use finer voxels in regions of interest for multiphysics applications. Adaptive Mesh Refinement (AMR) algorithms can use various solution metrics to seek an optimum mesh. Many AMR frameworks use isotropic refinement, dividing mesh elements in all dimensions even if the solution only varies in one dimension. This can result in unnecessarily refined meshes in some dimensions, increasing the computational demand to converge statistics. In this paper, we introduce an algorithm native to Multiphysics Object-Oriented Simulation Environment (MOOSE) and Cardinal that enables anisotropic amalgamation of elements for tallying during mesh adaptivity in the pursuit of saving computational resources. We also present a parametric study to demonstrate the effects of different clustering heuristics on element amalgamation, with diagnostic metrics to determine when the neutron tally resolution is conserved. We have found that clustering elements based on their tally similarity level has impact on anisotropic clustering and spatial resolution of solution preservation while simultaneously reducing the statistical uncertainty.

Keywords: Monte Carlo, neutron transport, mesh tally amalgamation, adaptive mesh refinement, clustering algorithms

1. INTRODUCTION

Monte Carlo neutron transport mimics the behavior of neutrons traveling inside a reactor, solving the Boltzmann neutron transport equation stochastically. This enables the use of continuous phase space variables, allowing high fidelity solutions. A very fine mesh may be required to resolve the details of the solution field. Naively, one may refine the mesh uniformly throughout the domain. As mesh elements become smaller, more computational resources are required to achieve acceptable statistical uncertainties. In order to refine only where necessary, Adaptive Mesh Refinement (AMR) takes a coarse mesh refines via metrics derived from the solution field [1]. The approach implemented by `libMesh` involves two systems, Indicators and Markers, which involve identifying mesh elements candidate for modification and then actually updating the mesh, respectively [2]. Indicators often evaluate some function of the solution, i.e gradient, current, extremes, etc. Markers then determine if an element should be refined or coarsened based on the metric calculated by the Indicator. While this can result in non-uniform refinement of the mesh, AMR techniques typically refine each mesh element isotropically even if the solution field doesn't require it. These unwanted elements demand additional computational resources, causing increases in the statistical error without sufficient particles reaching each region.

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By relaxing the requirement of isotropic refinement, there is an opportunity to improve statistics. This allows refinement to occur only in regions necessary to resolve gradients. This work seeks to study methods for anisotropic refinement. The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we discuss the preliminary algorithmic development for heuristic-driven element clustering, how to tally in these clusters, and development of evaluation matrix for mesh tally amalgamation solution. In Section 3, we describe our test problem, AMR strategy, and clustering heuristics. In Section 4 we present the results of the mesh tally amalgamation. Section 5 ends with the conclusions of this work and lays out next steps for future works.

2. MESH TALLY AMALGAMATION

2.1. Description of the Clustering Algorithm for Mesh Tally Amalgamation

In this study we implemented a clustering algorithm that identifies candidate elements to be grouped into clusters based on some solution heuristics native to Multiphysics Object-Oriented Simulation Environment (MOOSE) [3] and the Cardinal [4] framework. These groupings allow contributions from each region's tallies rather than requiring each element to score separately. Since the tally mean is computed across all elements in a cluster, the statistical uncertainty is reduced because the combined domain includes more tally scores than the individual elements alone. Figure 1 shows two clusters that might arise following the refinement of a parent mesh element.

In order to be clustered together, two elements must be neighbors, i.e. share one common face, and satisfy a heuristic-based comparison. The clustering sweep starts with the first active element in the mesh, which is then compared to its neighboring elements. If a pair of elements passes all the heuristic tests, then they are grouped into a cluster. A search over neighboring elements is performed until all the elements in a cluster are detected. This continues with the second active element and so on until each mesh element is clustered or visited. During the sweep, if an element is already labeled as part of a cluster, it is ignored. For some heuristics, the clustering process may be order-dependent; starting with different elements or traversing in different orders can lead to different clusters. For demonstration, we used a structured mesh, though the clustering algorithm applies to mesh types supported by libMesh and MOOSE.

Figure 1. Elements marked for mesh tally amalgamation in two clusters.

After clustering, the amalgamated mesh is used by OpenMC [5] for tallying. If a tally event occurs in a mesh element that is not part of a cluster, the score from that event is accumulated to that element as normal. If a tally event occurs in a mesh element that *is* part of a cluster, the score from that event is accumulated to the first element of that cluster, which corresponds to the cluster label. During tally normalization, the accumulated tally is copied to all other elements of the cluster for minimally-intrusive source code changes.

2.2. Evaluating Mesh Amalgamation

In an ideal case, mesh amalgamation should have small impacts on the accuracy of the results with large improvements in the statistical precision. One measure of the accuracy is the relative discrepancy

between the amalgamated solutions, $\Phi_{test}(\vec{r})$, and reference solutions, $\Phi_{ref}(\vec{r})$, on a mesh that has experienced the same degree of automated refinement, but without amalgamation. For each solution x , defined at any point \vec{r} on the domain, there is a mean value, $\mu_x(\vec{r})$ and a relative statistical uncertainty $R_x(\vec{r})$. In order to compare amalgamated solutions to a reference, we have considered a standalone OpenMC calculation on the non-amalgamated version of the mesh, where all the mesh element have same adaptivity hierarchy. The relative discrepancy for tally mean between mesh tally amalgamation and the reference solution is defined as,

$$\delta_\mu(\vec{r}) \equiv \frac{\mu_{test}(\vec{r}) - \mu_{ref}(\vec{r})}{\mu_{ref}(\vec{r})} = \frac{\mu_{test}(\vec{r})}{\mu_{ref}(\vec{r})} - 1 \quad (1)$$

It is useful to consider the magnitude of this relative discrepancy in the context of the relative statistical uncertainty by defining a z-score:

$$z(\vec{r}) \equiv \frac{\delta_\mu(\vec{r})}{R_{ref}(\vec{r})} \quad (2)$$

3. TEST PROBLEM

3.1. Problem Description

To test mesh tally amalgamation, we chose a 1-D 55 cm slab of natural uranium dioxide (UO_2) with $\rho_{UO_2} = 10$ g/cc adjacent to a 45 cm boron carbide (B_4C) region with $\rho_{B_4C} = 2.52$ g/cc. Since B_4C is a strong neutron absorber, the flux solution far away from the interface should have a low gradient. Due to the high absorption cross section, fewer neutrons reach the end of the B_4C region, so we expect higher statistical uncertainties near $x = 100$ cm. By selecting clustering heuristics that target constant flux regions with high uncertainty, a reduction in statistical uncertainty should be observed when these regions are amalgamated. The slab has vacuum boundaries at the minimum and maximum x planes and reflective boundaries on all outer y and z faces. Figure 2 shows a visual representation of the OpenMC model and the initial mesh. The OpenMC model descriptions and input files to recreate the results are available at https://github.com/magnoxemo/amr_test_cases_input_files.

Figure 2. OpenMC model and initial mesh of the slab (**Blue** = UO_2 and **Gray** = B_4C)

3.2. AMR Strategy Selection

This problem utilizes MOOSE's `ValueJumpIndicator`, which calculates the jump on element faces for a discontinuous field variable [1]. The value jump for an element i is given as,

$$e_{jump,i} = \sqrt{h_{max,i} \oint_{s_i} [[u_i]]^2 ds}, \quad (3)$$

where $e_{jump,i}$ is value jump estimate of the spatial error, S_i is the element surface, $[[u]]_i$ is the jump operator acting on the discontinuous tally variable u , and $h_{max,i}$ is the maximum vertex separation distance between two element which shares a common surface S_i . As stated earlier, this study aims to refine a mesh to resolve neutron flux tally gradients. The ValueJumpIndicator is sufficient for demonstration purposes, but other Indicators could be used. The ErrorFractionMarker in MOOSE refines an element if the cumulative error sum, given the error from a given element (from a list of elements sorted by spatial error), does not exceed a fraction of the total spatial error. The ValueThresholdMarker operates on the tally statistical error and only allows a given element to be refined if the statistical relative error is sufficiently low. A boolean AND of these two criteria is performed to ensure that an element is only marked for refinement if the spatial jump error is sufficiently large and the statistical error, R_x is below a threshold. The parameters used in this study can be found in Table I; we refer readers interested in this particular adaptivity scheme to [1] for additional details.

Table I. AMR settings

AMR Object	Parameters	Settings
ValueJumpIndicator	Neutron Flux	$e_{jump,i} = \sqrt{h_{max,i} \oint_{S_i} [[\Phi_i]]^2 ds}$
ErrorFractionMarker	$e_{jump,i}$ and $f = 0.2$	$(1 - f) \times \max(e_{jump}) < e_{jump,i} < \max(e_{jump})$
ValueThresholdMarker	$R_x(\vec{r})$ and threshold = 0.05	$R_x(\vec{r}) < \text{threshold}$

3.3. Clustering Heuristics

For mesh tally amalgamation, the most effective clustering strategy will be where the tally values show a negligible tally gradient or approximate uniformity, but large tally uncertainties. This attempts to ensure spatial resolution preservation of the tally. The mean tally relative difference of two adjacent elements is given by,

$$\Gamma_{i,j} = \frac{|(\Phi_i - \Phi_j)|}{\Phi_i} \quad (4)$$

where the indices i and j represent two adjacent elements in the mesh. Elements are clustered while sweeping through the mesh. An pair of elements with index (i, j) are added to a cluster, if $\Gamma(i, j)$ is less than a threshold value, and their tally relative statistical error, $R_{test}(\vec{r})$ is within an upper fraction, ϵ , of the global tally relative error. Effectively, for any element pair (i, j) to be clustered together, they must resolve the following,

$$\begin{cases} \Gamma_{i,j} < \Gamma_{\text{threshold}} \\ R_{\text{test}}^i > \epsilon(R_{\text{test}}^{\text{max}} - R_{\text{test}}^{\text{min}}) + R_{\text{test}}^{\text{min}} \\ R_{\text{test}}^j > \epsilon(R_{\text{test}}^{\text{max}} - R_{\text{test}}^{\text{min}}) + R_{\text{test}}^{\text{min}} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

A parameter study was performed to determine the effect of $\Gamma_{\text{threshold}}$ and ϵ on cluster formation on the diagnostic metrics discussed earlier. The parameter space for clustering heuristics in this study are $\Gamma_{\text{threshold}} \in \{0.05, 0.1, 0.2\}$ and $\epsilon \in \{0.4, 0.5\}$.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This test model has reflective boundary conditions on all faces besides the x-planes bounding the slab to simulation a one-dimensional neutron transport problem. The materials selected aim to create a system with a decaying flux distribution in the B_4C region as particles get further from the interface. Thus, the flux gradient near the end of the B_4C block becomes relatively flat compared to the UO_2 region and the interface. Due to absorption, the Monte Carlo solution near the end of the B_4C block yields

Figure 3. Reference solution

Figure 4. Heuristic calculations for Cluster 18 (test case $\Gamma_{threshold} = 0.1$, $\epsilon = 0.5$)

higher relative statistical uncertainty. The neutron flux and statistical uncertainty distribution for a reference solution generated using conventional AMR with the strategy described in section 3.2 is given in Figure 3.

In the test case corresponding to $\Gamma_{threshold} = 0.1$ and $\epsilon = 0.4$, two clusters are observed near the edge of the mesh as shown in the top mesh plot in figure 4a. The middle and the bottom mesh plots portrait the statistical error distribution of mesh amalgamation test case and reference test case, respectively, using the same color map. Statistical uncertainty and tally value should be same in non clustered elements since mesh tally amalgamation only tallies the clustered elements together. It is necessary to cross-check that these clustering heuristics are behaving as expected. To validate clustering behavior, we have taken the previous adaptivity step solution and calculated the mean tally relative difference between all of the elements in cluster 18 ($\Gamma_{threshold} = 0.1$ and $\epsilon = 0.5$). The maximum flux tally statistical relative error in the previous adaptivity step was $R_{test}^{max} = 0.073$; in order to form a cluster all elements under consideration must have $R_{test}(\vec{r}) > R_{test}^{max} \times (1 - \epsilon) = 0.036$ and $\Gamma_{i,j} < \Gamma_{threshold} = 0.1$. The calculated heuristics are in agreement with Equation (5) as illustrated in Figure 4.

Next, a parametric analysis of clustering parameters and observed changes will be presented. The change of the spatial solution in amalgamated regions and the corresponding uncertainties will be explored while varying $\Gamma_{threshold}$ and ϵ . $\Gamma_{threshold}$ defines the allowable mean flux relative difference between neighboring elements that can be merged into a single cluster, given by Equation (4). Lower values of $\Gamma_{threshold}$ apply a more strict condition to avoid clustering neighbor elements that have higher flux gradients. Using a stricter $\Gamma_{threshold}$ attempts to preserve spatial resolution of solutions. In Figure 5a and Figure 5b or Figure 4, for a fixed $\epsilon = 0.5$, a lower value for $\Gamma_{threshold} = 0.05$ shows more clustering

anisotropy than $\Gamma_{\text{threshold}} \in \{0.1, 0.2\}$. As the clustering in 5b and 4 are same, they have the same solution and statistical error distribution. Additionally, in Figure 5c and Figure 5d, we also see the same clustering pattern, indicating that the sensitive value for mean tally relative difference is less than 0.1 in that region. $\Gamma_{\text{threshold}} = 0.05$ forms two new clusters with IDs of 18 and 78, while $\Gamma_{\text{threshold}} \in \{0.1, 0.2\}$ forms either a single cluster or no cluster with those elements.

Figure 5. Changes of clustering pattern and R_{test} due to different values of Γ and ϵ **Top:** Element Clusters, **Middle:** R_{test} , **Bottom:** R_{ref} (Cluster ID = -1 means that element isn't part of a cluster)

In amalgamated regions, the neutron flux distribution and its statistical error depends on the clustering behavior. If different combinations of $\Gamma_{\text{threshold}}$ and ϵ create the same clusters, the flux and statistical error distribution will be the same. Setting $\epsilon = 0.4$ and $\epsilon = 0.5$ while varying $\Gamma_{\text{threshold}}$ within the range $[0.1, 0.2]$ independently results in identical clusters, yielding the same flux discrepancy and statistical error. Figure 6 and Figure 7 illustrate the δ_{μ} and R_{test} distribution along x axis. We observe a drop in uncertainty in Figure 6b for the last two clusters of element at the edge of B_4C slab, where element clusters are formed. In Figure 7b a decrease in the statistical uncertainty is observed as a single cluster is formed for the test case $(\Gamma_{\text{threshold}}, \epsilon) = (0.1, 0.4)$ in Figure 5c. In test case $(\Gamma_{\text{threshold}}, \epsilon) = (0.05, 0.5)$ we notice formation of two independent clusters (IDs of 78 and 18) in Figure 5a which also reduces statistical uncertainty in the amalgamated regions. Additional clustering anisotropy is also observed in this region, which preserves the spatial resolution of the flux profile over the cases where $(\Gamma_{\text{threshold}}, \epsilon) = (0.1, 0.5)$ or $(\Gamma_{\text{threshold}}, \epsilon) = (0.2, 0.5)$.

Figure 6. δ_μ and R_{test} profile along x axis for test case $(\Gamma_{threshold}, \epsilon) = (0.1, 0.5)$

Figure 7. δ_μ and R_{test} profile along x axis for test case $(\Gamma_{threshold}, \epsilon) = (0.1, 0.4)$

Figure 8. δ_μ and R_{test} profile along x axis for test case $(\Gamma_{threshold}, \epsilon) = (0.05, 0.5)$

An effective way to evaluate if mesh tally clustering is preserving the resolution of the neutron flux distribution is to quantify the z score from Equation (2). Figure 9 illustrates the z scores for test cases $(\Gamma_{threshold}, \epsilon) = (0.05, 0.5)$, $(\Gamma_{threshold}, \epsilon) = (0.1, 0.5)$ and $(\Gamma_{threshold}, \epsilon) = (0.1, 0.4)$. 71.88% of elements in the cluster located at $x = 92.5$ have a $|Z|$ -score less than 2. All of the amalgamated elements at $x = 92.5$ for test case $(\Gamma_{threshold}, \epsilon) = (0.05, 0.5)$ have a $|Z|$ -score less than three. This indicates that clustering anisotropy preserves more flux resolution than isotropic clustering while reducing the uncertainty as illustrated in Figure 8. On the other hand, the cluster located at $x = 97.5$ has far larger dispersion in $|Z|$ -score results than the cluster located at $x = 92.5$. Two of the elements in the cluster located at $x = 97.5$ had a $|Z|$ -score larger than three, indicating that amalgamating these elements altered the flux distribution beyond the 99.7% or 3σ confidence interval.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The mesh tally amalgamation algorithm presented in this work is still in early stages of development. While the mean flux relative difference, Γ , is related to the spatial flux gradient, it doesn't take account

Figure 9. $|Z|$ -score in amalgamated elements, with centers $x = 92.5$ and $x = 97.5$, respectively.

of the spatial difference between elements. One of our test cases, $\Gamma_{\text{threshold}} = 0.05$, showed clustering anisotropy is necessary for preserving flux resolution while succeeding in reducing statistical tally uncertainty. On the other hand, $\Gamma_{\text{threshold}} = \{0.1, 0.2\}$ and $\epsilon = \{0.4, 0.5\}$ cases formed isotropic clustering meaning that sensitivity limit for anisotropic clustering was below 0.1. For a given problem, to have successful mesh tally amalgamation, it is important to dynamically explore sensitivity limits before clustering. There is still future work to study clustering heuristics that seek to find low gradient regions. For multiphysics coupled AMR cases, mesh tally amalgamation should also use the Markers system to gain anisotropic clustering. The interaction of neutronic-thermal-fluid feedback and mesh amalgamation still has room to be studied, seeking to create optimum meshes for each physics involved in a coupling scheme. The importance of using meshes that adequately capture gradients is more important when multiphysics feedback is involved and future works will seek to evaluate heuristics that succeed in solving each physics while creating efficient meshes.

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